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Radiation hardness and annealing study of neutron-irradiated silicon photomultipliers

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ABSTRACT: Silicon photomultipliers (SiPMs) are semiconductor photodetectors increasingly used in high-energy physics experiments. In the planned upgrade of the Large Hadron Collider beauty (LHCb) experiment, they are considered to be used to detect Cherenkov photons in the Ring Imaging Cherenkov (RICH) detectors. In this application, the biggest drawback of current SiPMs is their susceptibility to radiation damage, where the dark count rate (DCR), typically on the order of 10^5 Hz/mm² at room temperature, significantly increases proportionally with the irradiation fluence, which hinders the single photon detection beyond fluence of 10^9 neq/cm². In this work, 3×3 mm² SiPMs from different producers and cell sizes, Hamamatsu (50 μ m, S13360-3050PE), Ketek (25 μ m, PM3325-WB and 50 μ m, PM3350-EB), AdvanSiD (40 μ m, NUV3S-P and RGB3S-P), SensL (35 μ m, MicroFJ-30035), a 3.7×3.7 mm² SiPM from Broadcom (30 μ m, AFBR-S4N44C013), and a 1×1 mm² SiPM from SensL (35 μ m, MicroRA-10035) were characterized. The SiPMs were irradiated at the Jožef Stefan Institute TRIGA nuclear reactor with fluences from 10^9 neq/cm² up to 10^{13} neq/cm². The main objective was to determine the temperature at which irradiated SiPMs can still meet minimal performance requirements in future RICH detectors. The influence of the high-temperature annealing on SiPM performance post-irradiation was also investigated. For the SiPM characterization in all the cases, current-voltage (I-V curve) measurements, DCR measurements, and waveform analysis, including single photon time resolution (SPTR), were carried out at controlled temperature steps from room temperature down to the liquid nitrogen temperature. As a result, through a combination of annealing and cooling, 2 of the SiPMs withstood the highest irradiation fluence of 10^{13} neq/cm² with an SPTR of about 200 ps.

KEYWORDS: Cryogenic detectors; Radiation-hard detectors; Cherenkov detectors; Timing detectors; Front-end electronics for detector readout; Digital signal processing

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1 Introduction

Silicon photomultipliers (SiPMs) are semiconductor photodetectors that can be used in a broad spectrum of fields like high-energy physics, nuclear medicine, and space applications [1–3]. For the next generation of high-energy physics experiments, such as the Large Hadron Collider beauty (LHCb) experiment upgrade 2, with an expected luminosity of $1.5 \times 10^{34} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ [4], the SiPMs are considered potential candidates suitable to detect Cherenkov photons in the Ring Imaging Cherenkov (RICH) detectors. For this application, the major drawback of the SiPMs is their susceptibility to harsh radiation environments, where the dark count rate (DCR) is expected to significantly increase proportionally to the neutron irradiation fluence. As a consequence, beyond about 10^9 1-MeV neutron equivalent per cm^2 (neq/cm^2), it is not possible to resolve single photons at room temperature [5, 6] which brings challenges for particle identification. To some degree, mitigation techniques such as high-temperature annealing and cooling can recover the SiPM performance after the irradiation [7].

In this contribution, SiPMs from different producers and cell sizes were characterized at room temperature and at controlled temperature steps down to the liquid nitrogen temperature before the irradiation, after the irradiation with different fluences from $10^9 \text{ neq}/\text{cm}^2$ up to $10^{13} \text{ neq}/\text{cm}^2$, and after the annealing. The irradiation was conducted in steps with a single SiPM sample per producer and cell size. After each irradiation step, low-temperature annealing (60°C for 2 h) was carried out before SiPM re-characterization, and after the $10^{13} \text{ neq}/\text{cm}^2$ irradiation step, additional high-temperature annealing (200°C for 20 h) was performed. The main purpose was to determine if the SiPMs under study can meet minimal performance requirements in future RICH detectors (DCR low enough to still allow single photon discrimination and an SPTR of ~ 250 ps FWHM) and under what operational conditions.

2 Experimental setup

The experimental setup used for SiPM characterization is an upgrade of the setup previously used for measuring $1 \times 1 \text{ mm}^2$ FBK NUV-HD-RH SiPMs [8, 9]. The current measurements as a function of the bias voltage (V_{bias}) were performed in the dark using a KEITHLEY 6517B electrometer, while the DCR measurements as a function of different SiPM pulse height thresholds were carried out using a chain of modular electronics with the particularity that the pulse width output of the discriminator was set to the lowest possible value (~ 10 ns), which allows DCR measurements up to 100 MHz. For the waveform analysis, the SiPM signals were digitized using a DRS4 evaluation board with 10^6 waveforms collected per measurement. The foremost differences compared to the

setup previously used and described in [9] are in the radio-frequency (RF) shielding box (figure 1), adapted to consider the specific geometry of the new SiPMs under study, their packaging and the requirements for cooling down to the liquid nitrogen temperature. In this regard, the SiPMs were thermalized with the RF shielding box through their own pins. Besides, a new in-house produced electronics board using μ PC2710TB-E3-A pre-amplifier [10] was pre-shielded by enclosing it in its own aluminium box inside the RF shielding box in an attempt to minimize the electronic noise and feedback. The breakdown voltage (V_{br}) at room temperature was estimated from the first inflection point in the reverse I-V curves, while for the remaining controlled temperature steps, it was calculated following the producer specified temperature coefficient.

Figure 1. Experimental setup: the SiPM and the new custom electronics board inside the latest radio-frequency shielding box.

3 Results

The behaviour shown in figure 2 for the I-V curve measurements of 2 of the characterized SiPMs is representative of the rest of the SiPMs under study. Before the irradiation, the current had a very soft dependence on the V_{bias} until the V_{br} , and after the V_{br} , it exponentially increased until an overvoltage (OV) of about 8 V, where correlated noise takes over. After the irradiation, the I-V curve measurements showed the neutron damage effects between irradiation fluences: the current significantly increased, and for almost all the SiPMs, except for the $1 \times 1 \text{ mm}^2$ SensL ($35 \mu\text{m}$) SiPM, a $\leq 0.5 \text{ V}$ decrease in the V_{br} was observed, mostly after 10^{11} neq/cm^2 . After the high-temperature annealing, a noteworthy drop in the leakage current (non-multiplied current) was measured.

Figure 2. I-V curve measurements for SiPMs of different producers before the irradiation, after the irradiation, and after the high-temperature annealing: SensL ($35 \mu\text{m}$) (left) and AdvanSiD-NUV ($40 \mu\text{m}$) (right).

Prior to the SiPM irradiation, the DCR was between 1 MHz and 4 MHz at room temperature, which decreased to less than 100 kHz by cooling down to at least -60°C (figure 3, top). After

the irradiation, the DCR strongly increased, reaching values over 10 MHz at room temperature beyond fluence of 10^{13} neq/cm². Along with this, the steps in the threshold scan, representing different numbers of triggered cells, disappeared. Cooling helps to decrease the DCR, but beyond fluence of 10^{13} neq/cm² (figure 3, bottom-left), the steps can not be observed even at the liquid nitrogen temperature, except for the 3×3 mm² Hamamatsu (50 μ m) SiPM. Besides, except for the 3×3 mm² AdvanSiD-NUV (40 μ m) SiPM, a significant reduction in the DCR was measured after the high-temperature annealing (figure 3, bottom-right), reaching, for example, ~ 1 MHz at -100°C with the 3×3 mm² Hamamatsu (50 μ m) SiPM.

Figure 3. DCR measurements for the SiPMs under study at 5 V overvoltage unless specified: before the irradiation (top), after the irradiation at the highest irradiation fluence of 10^{13} neq/cm² (bottom-left), and after the high-temperature annealing (bottom-right).

Before any irradiation, the single photon time resolution (SPTR) at room temperature and an overvoltage of 5 V for the 3×3 mm² SiPMs characterized in this work is at worst about 400 ps, e.g., 399 ps for the Broadcom (30 μ m) SiPM and 356 ps for the Ketek (25 μ m) SiPM, while at best it is under 200 ps, e.g., 187 ps for the Hamamatsu (50 μ m) SiPM and 163 ps for the AdvanSiD-NUV (40 μ m) SiPM. Besides, also before any irradiation, while operating the 1×1 mm² SensL (35 μ m) SiPM at an overvoltage of 9 V (figure 4), an SPTR of 246 ps was measured at room temperature which improved to 110 ps by cooling down to liquid nitrogen temperature. As expected, after the irradiation, the single photons could not be resolved anymore at room temperature. However, up to the irradiation fluence of 10^{11} neq/cm², through a combination of low-temperature annealing (2 h at 60°C between irradiations) and cooling, single photon discrimination can be regained and, with it, an SPTR consistent with the value before any irradiation, except for the AdvanSiD-NUV (40 μ m) SiPM for which it deteriorates to above 300 ps after 10^{11} neq/cm².

Figure 4. For the 1×1 mm² SensL (35 μ m) SiPM operated at an overvoltage of 9 V before the irradiation, after the irradiation at different fluences, and after the high-temperature annealing: signal shape at room temperature or liquid nitrogen temperature (left); charge distribution at the temperature in which under each specific condition the single photon cut (shown in red) was still possible (middle); and timing distribution at the operational temperature selected, with the SPTR expressed in FWHM (right).

Additionally, beyond fluence of 10^{13} neq/cm², the single photon cut could only be done for 2 of the SiPMs under study, the 3×3 mm² Hamamatsu (50 μ m) SiPM and the 1×1 mm² SensL (35 μ m) SiPM for which the measured SPTR was 218 ps and 210 ps, respectively. Moreover, by a combination

of high-temperature annealing carried out at 200°C for 20 h and cooling, single photon discrimination was regained for the $3 \times 3 \text{ mm}^2$ Ketek (25 μm) SiPM and the $3 \times 3 \text{ mm}^2$ SensL (35 μm) SiPM but the SPTR was above 300 ps. It should, however, be noted that, following such high-temperature annealing, the physical appearance of all the SiPMs under study turned yellowish or completely dark.

4 Conclusions

In this work, neutron-irradiated SiPMs from different producers and cell sizes were characterized. The results show that through a combination of low-temperature annealing and cooling down to cryogenic temperatures, only 2 of the studied SiPMs, the $3 \times 3 \text{ mm}^2$ Hamamatsu (50 μm) SiPM and the $1 \times 1 \text{ mm}^2$ SensL (35 μm) SiPM, were able to withstand the highest irradiation fluence of 10^{13} neq/cm^2 with an SPTR of about 200 ps. It is, however, challenging to differentiate effects originating from the SiPMs and those originating in the electronics, as they are both exposed to the low temperatures. Further studies are thus needed to clarify the open questions.

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